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PVC-PMMA Electrolyte System Tailoring with Different Dopants: A Comprehensive Study

Abstract: - Polyvinyl chloride (PVC) and polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) are types of plastic materials widely used in various scientific and technological fields. In this study, we prepared thin films of PVC and PMMA by doping them with oxalic acid (OA) and cinnamic acid (CA) adopting the isothermal evaporation method. The thickness of the thin films was calculated using a digital micro-meter screw gauge. We characterized the thin films using analytical techniques including Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) spectroscopy, scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and X-ray diffraction (XRD). FT-IR spectrum analysis confirmed the successful formation of homogeneous 1:1 (PVC: PMMA) thin films by observing characteristic peaks resulting from the addition of oxalic acid and cinnamic acid. XRD analysis revealed that all thin films had an amorphous nature. The scanning electron micrograph images of the samples supported the results obtained from FT-IR and XRD analyses.

Keywords: PVC-PMMA Electrolyte, (C₂H₂O₄), C₉H₈O₂, Analytical Techniques

I. INTRODUCTION

Polymers and their mixtures are a diverse class of materials that have wide applications in various industries [1–5]. The way these materials are synthesized has a major influence on their molecular structure and, consequently, their properties. Understanding these synthesis methods is crucial to adapting polymers to specific requirements. In addition, the electrical conductivity and dielectric properties of polymers are of the utmost importance, especially in areas such as electronics and energy storage. The ability to modify these properties through doping, the integration of nanomaterials, and the design of structures opens up opportunities for innovation.

Polymer electrolytes, a type of plastic material, have garnered significant attention due to their versatile uses in different scientific and technological sectors. The unique characteristics and versatile nature of polymer electrolytes make them a valuable material for numerous applications, driving ongoing research and technological advancements in this area. Hence, a polymer electrolyte, defined as a membrane made of salts dissolved polymer matrix which having in a high-molecular-weight, is known as a polymer electrolyte [6]. These ionic conduction-friendly, solid, solvent-free systems find extensive use in a range of electrochemical tools, such as lithium-ion batteries and solid-state and rechargeable batteries.

Fenton *et al.* originally introduced the notion of preparing polymer electrolytes in 1973 [7], but S. Rao *et al.* [8] realized and understood their technological relevance a few years later. The first polyelectrolyte to be suggested and investigated for solid polymer electrolyte (SPE) Li rechargeable batteries was poly (ethylene oxide) [9, 10]. The majority of solid polymer electrolytes (SPEs) are made either by dispersion in the solid state. Additionally, an effort is made to use covalent bonding or another chemical or physical technique to block the anion in the polymer medium [11].

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Polymer electrolytes comprise a wide range of substances that are specially designed to fulfill particular needs and uses in electrochemical devices. These electrolytes are generated by complexing low-lattice energy

salts with solvent polymers [12-13]. Chemical and physical methods are the two main types of polymer film production technology. The flexibility is provided by the electrolytes of solid polymers, which can be easily produced as soft films with a thickness of only a few microns. This allows continuous contact with solid electrodes throughout the operation, facilitating the creation and deployment of various electrochemical devices. The preparation of polymer films is the main topic of this research. Many techniques for producing high-quality polymer films have been described in literature and some really good reviews are available [14-16].

The characteristics, compositions, and ion transport methods of these materials differ, giving rise to several types of polymer electrolytes. Typical polymer electrolyte types include [17-18]. Poly(ethylene oxide), Poly(vinyl alcohol), Poly(methyl methacrylate), Poly(caprolactone), Poly(chitosan), Poly(vinyl pyrrolidone), Poly(vinyl chloride), Poly(vinylidene fluoride), and Poly(imide) are a few typical polymers utilized in these electrolytes. These polymers can all be customized for certain uses and have distinctive qualities.

Polymer electrolytes are fundamental components in many fields, including biomedical engineering, energy storage, electrochemical conversion, sensing, and actuation [19-22]. They are essential for tackling societal issues and promoting technological innovation in a variety of sectors due to their special set of properties.

Also, dopants play vital role in changing electrical parameters like electrical conductivities, which includes ac as well as dc, and dielectric constant. Values of these parameters will determine which applications the desired material will be used. In this study, the same polymer electrolyte system has two different types of dopants. If these dopants completely miscible in polymer electrolyte then it will definitely causes electrical parameters of casting thin films [23-25]. Only the idea of dopant miscibility in specific polymer electrolytes will be examined in this thorough investigation.

II. MATERIAL AND EXPERIMENTAL

All chemicals were of AR grade. Polyvinyl chloride (PVC) and Polymethyl methacrylates (PMMA) were supplied by SIGMA –ALDRICH, Co., USA having purity 99.99%. . While, oxalic acid and cinnamic acid by Merck specialties private limited, India and Tetrahydrofuran by E-Merck India Ltd., India is being used as a solvent for mixing process of two base materials PVC and PMMA. . In this work, the isothermal evaporation process was used to cast thin films [26-29].

A. Preparation of Thin Films

1) Preparation of a 1:1 (PVC-PMMA) Base Polyblend Thin Film

In this work, the isothermal evaporation technique has been used due to the rapid and easy mixing process. The two polymers, PVC and PMMA, have been taken with different weight ratios (i.e. 1:1) as required, and dissolved in the same solvent, tetrahydrofuran (THF). To create a homogeneous solution, the solution was let to stand for three to four days, allowing the polymers to fully dissolve. A glass plate (10 cm x 10 cm) was thoroughly cleaned with water and later with acetone as the substrate. In order to achieve a perfect level (and uniform thickness of the films), a pool of mercury was used in a plastic tray. After being placed onto the glass plate, the solution was given time to evenly spread across the substrate in all directions. The complete assembly was kept at ambient temperature in a dust-free environment. As a result, the solvent in the mixture was left to totally evaporate and turn into dried air. After removing the film from the glass substrate and splitting it into small, appropriate-sized pieces, the surface contaminants were eliminated by acetone rinsing. In this way, the films were prepared with the isothermal evaporation process.

2) Preparation of 1:1 (PVC-PMMA) Polyblend Thin Films Using Dopant Oxalic Acid (OA)

The two polymers PVC and PMMA were taken in weight ratio 1:1, and dopant oxalic acid was taken in doping percentage 5%. All three were dissolved separately in a 10 ml THF solution. After allowing them to completely dissolve, all three solutions were mixed together. A glass plate (10 cm x 10 cm) was cleaned with hot water and then used as a substrate with acetone. To achieve a perfect leveling and uniformity in the thickness of the film, a pool of mercury was used in the plastic box in which the glass plate was placed. After being placed onto the glass plate, the solution was given time to evenly spread across the substrate in all directions. The complete assembly was kept at ambient temperature in a dust-free environment. As a result, the solvent in the mixture was left to totally evaporate and turn into dried air. After removing the film from the glass substrate and splitting it into small, appropriate-sized pieces, the surface contaminants were eliminated by acetone rinsing. In this way, the films were prepared with the isothermal evaporation process.

3) Preparation of 1: 1 (PVC-PMMA) Polyblend Thin Films Using Dopant Cinnamic Acid (CA)

The 5 % of cinnamic acid (dopant) was taken and soluble in the mixture of PVC-PMMA solutions. After attainment homogenous solution, the above mentioned above (2) procedure was repeated to prepare the film using isothermal evaporation technique.

B. Measurements and Analytical Characterizations

The thickness of film is crucial for their structural and electrical properties. Various techniques can be used to measure film thickness. In this study, the thickness of all the samples was calculated using a Digital micrometer provided by Mitutoyo Corporation in Japan. This micrometer has a precision of 0.001 mm and a measurement range of 0 to 25 mm. It can be operated between 50°C and 400°C, with an instrumental error of +2 μm at 20°C. Additionally, it features a digital display with 6 digits and a minus sign for easy and clear readings.

Three samples were chosen for further investigation from a series based on optimization study results. Table 1 contains a list of optimized samples along with their weight percentage, sample codes, and thicknesses.

Table 1 Sample codes and thickness of 1:1 (PVC-PMMA) composite thin films doped with oxalic acid and cinnamic acid

Sr. No	Sample description	Sample code	Thickness
1	1:1 (PVC-PMMA)	S ₁	0.041 mm
2	1:1 (PVC-PMMA) OA 5%	S ₂	0.024 mm
3	1:1 (PVC-PMMA) CA 5%	S ₃	0.073 mm

The films' ultraviolet (UV) absorption spectra were obtained at ambient temperature. FT-IR measurements were conducted using the Bruker Model: Vertex 70, which has a wide wave number range (50 cm^{-1} to 15,000 cm^{-1}). This equipment allows recordings in both transmission and reflection geometries, with a high resolution scale of 0.5 cm^{-1} . The FT-IR spectra of all samples fall within the range of 500-4000 cm^{-1} .

XRD is analytical technique that provides valuable insights into the lattice structure of a material. It provides details on the phases, average grain size, crystallinity, and crystal flaws, among other structural characteristics. In this study, X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) of the samples was performed by the Bruker D8 Advance XRD system, obtained from the UGC-DAE Consortium for Scientific Research, Indore. Scanning electron microscopy was also carried out at the Department of Physics; RTM Nagpur University, by the Philips Model: XL-30. This analysis aimed to examine the surface structure, identify defects and how much miscibility of dopant presents in the samples.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. FT-IR Spectroscopic Analysis

In current study, FTIR Bruker Model: Vertex 70 was use in the transmittance mode from 500 cm^{-1} – 4000 cm^{-1} . To get the FTIR profiles, the final scan was recorded by averaging 100 scans at a resolution of 8.0. The measurements obtained a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} .

In our case, we have studied the FTIR of samples having 1:1 (PVC: PMMA), 1:1 (PVC: PMMA) OA 5%, 1:1 (PVC: PMMA) CA 5%. Fig. 1, 2 and 3 shows FTIR spectra of sample S₁, S₂ and S₃ respectively.

Figure 1 FT-IR of S₁ Sample

Fig. 1 shows 1:1 (PVC: PMMA) spectra. The PMMA carbonyl band has slightly shifted to a lower wave number, according to the spectra. The shift of peak is about 4-6 cm^{-1} within the domain of miscibility of the two polymers. The miscibility of 1:1 (PVC: PMMA) is due to a specific interaction of the hydrogen bonding type between Carbonyl (C = O) of PMMA and hydrogen (from CHCl) group of PVC [30].

Figure 2 FT-IR of S₂ Sample

Fig. 2 shows 1:1 (PVC: PMMA) OA 5% spectra. The peak location for C = O stretching (i.e. 1732.08 cm⁻¹) in thin film shows minor shifting for the blend within the domain of miscibility.

Figure 3 FT-IR of S₃ Sample

While Fig. 3 shows 1:1 (PVC: PMMA) CA 5% spectra. It shows large number peaks at different positions, so it may causes to shift for the blend within the domain of immiscibility [31.32].

B. XRD Analysis

XRD patterns of all samples were taken, and all the sample spectra show a similar nature. So for simplicity only three XRD spectra are shown here. XRD pattern of 1:1 (PVC: PMMA), 1:1 (PVC: PMMA) OA 5%, 1:1 (PVC: PMMA) CA 5% are shown in Fig. 4, 5 and 6 respectively.

Figure 4 XRD of S₁ Sample

Figure 6 XRD of S₃ Sample

Generally, a polymer consists of both a crystalline region and an amorphous region. The conductivity parameter of the polymeric materials is characterized by their amorphous nature.

From Fig. 4, 5, and 6, it can be observed that the sample exhibit noisy spectra. A peak was observed around 25°, which is attributed to the amorphous nature [33, 34]. Therefore, the X-ray diffractograms of all the samples confirm the amorphous nature, showing large diffraction maxima that decrease at larger diffraction angles. The first main maximum shape indicates the order of the polymer chain packaging. The intensity and shape of the second maximum are related to the order effect within the main chain. The large humps observed in the XRD spectrum indicate the existence of very small crystallites. The absence of any prominent peak in the films demonstrates the mainly amorphous nature of the films. This is in agreement with many reports [35, 36].

C. Scanning Electron Microscopy

Scanning electron micrographs of blended materials were taken across composition for the 1: 1 (PVC: PMMA) blends are shown Fig. 7, 8 and 9. Micrographs show a heterogeneous structure of two base materials i.e. PVC and PMMA, but the size of the dispersed phase changes with composition.

As expected, the pore size maximums for the sample S₁ polymer blend. The tendency of PVC and PMMA to combine is revealed by the change in shape of particles from a spherical shape. As a result, PMMA coordinates with PVC and forms a complexation. In a literature survey, it was found that a higher pore size leads to less phase separation and forms a more homogeneous polymer electrolyte system [37, 38].

Figure 9 SEM Micrograph of S₃ Sample

Additionally, the morphology of the blends shows a phase-separated region, as shown in Fig. 7. Therefore, at the same concentration of PVC and PMMA, the phase split-up ultimately leads to the miscibility of the blend.

Fig. 8 and 9 clearly show that the 1:1 (PVC: PMMA) blend contains some impurities compared to Fig. 7. From a comparative study of Fig. 8 and 9, it is also observed that the dopant oxalic acid is more miscible as compared to cinnamic acid in 1:1 (PVC:PMMA) solution. Therefore, it can be concluded that the 1:1 (PVC: PMMA) blend with 5% oxalic acid forms a more homogeneous mixture, leading to the formation of a homogeneous thin film of PVC: PMMA with oxalic acid as a dopant. On the other hand, in the case of the 1:1 (PVC: PMMA) blend with 5% cinnamic acid, a homogeneous mixture was not formed, resulting in a thin film that was not homogeneous. This is because the thin film of the 1:1 (PVC: PMMA) blend with 5% cinnamic acid still shows some crystal particles of cinnamic acid, indicating that cinnamic acid was not completely miscible, i.e., immiscible with the 1:1 (PVC: PMMA) solution. This can also be explained by the fact that immiscible mixtures show several glass transition temperature areas, whereas miscible blends only show one [39].

IV. CONCLUSIONS

It was found that 1:1 (PVC: PMMA) CA 5% show maximum thickness among other samples. In short, in given study successfully casted the composites thin films of 1:1 (PVC: PMMA) with dopant oxalic acid (OA) and cinnamic acid (CA). The FT-IR spectrum study agrees us to conclude that successful formation of 1:1 (PVC: PMMA) homogenous thin films with OA and CA as dopant and characteristic peaks shows with addition of oxalic acid and cinnamic acid. XRD analysis shows amorphous nature all thin films. SEM micrographs of samples attribute FTIR and XRD's results. Also, the thin film of the 1:1 (PVC: PMMA) blend with 5% cinnamic acid still shows some crystal particles of cinnamic acid, indicating that cinnamic acid was not completely miscible, i.e., immiscible with the 1:1 (PVC: PMMA) solution. This can also be explained by the fact that immiscible mixes show several glass transition temperature areas, whereas miscible blends only show one [39]. As miscibility of dopant in polymer electrolyte system increase which cause to change in electrical parameters like electrical conductivities (AC and DC) and dielectric constant [40, 41].

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